

Supplementary Methods

Filtering SNPs and small indels

We first filtered the nuclear, mitochondrial, and chloroplast callsets using two filtering steps described in the GATK Best Practices Workflow for germline short variant discovery. The nuclear callset was filtered using the GATK modules VariantRecalibrator and ApplyVQSR (`-truth-sensitivity-filter-level 99.9`), using a set of variants called in a world-wide panel of 1135 *A. thaliana* accessions (The 1001 Genomes Consortium, 2016) as a training and truth set (`prior=10.0`) during recalibration. Additionally, nuclear, mitochondrial, and chloroplast variants were filtered with GATK SelectVariants using a set of hard thresholds. To choose suitable thresholds, we generated density plots of four variant annotations known to be informative for identifying false positive calls (quality normalized by read depth (QD), Fisher’s exact test of strand bias (FS), symmetric odds ratio test of strand bias (SOR), mapping quality (MQ)). Based on these plots (Figure S2), the following filtering thresholds were chosen for each callset:

- Chloroplast: QD < 22.0, FS > 50.0, SOR > 2.5, MQ < 35.0
- Mitochondrial: QD < 2.0, FS > 100.0, SOR > 4.0, MQ < 20.0
- Nuclear: QD < 20.0, FS > 70.0, SOR > 3.0, MQ < 30.0

After these steps, we could still observe SNPs and small indels that appeared to be unsupported by read alignments and would be considered *de novo* mutations, because they were found in single samples only. To remove such likely false positives, we applied additional filters based on genotype quality (GQ), which serves as a measure of the number of reads supporting a particular call and the percentage of samples having a genotype defined as “missing” at a particular site. To explore how these two filters affect the number of retained SNPs and indels, we computed the mean mutation rate of samples of each treatment using different combinations of thresholds for the minimum GQ (20, 30, 40) and maximum allowed percentage of missing genotypes (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50). While absolute mutation rates change between thresholds, relative differences between treatments are retained (Figure S3). To maximize sensitivity for putative adaptive variants, we chose to perform further analyses on variants obtained using the most lenient thresholds (minimum GQ: 20, maximum percentage of missing genotypes: 50).

Genotyping and merging CNVs

Overlapping CNV calls were merged into a single call if they fulfilled the following conditions: they were of the same type; their breakpoints were located within 1000 bp of each other on both the 5’ and 3’ end; they share at least 50% reciprocal overlap with each other (does not apply to insertions); and the distance between the insertion sites is no more than 10 bp (only applies to dispersed duplications and insertions). The read depth of each site in each line, relative to the 1000 bp flanking regions, was computed using `duphold` (Pedersen & Quinlan, 2019) (v0.2.1). These read depths were then used to refine the genotype calls in each line. Deletions were considered to be homozygous if they had a read depth lower than 0.25, heterozygous if they had a relative read depth between 0.25 and 0.7, and non-variant if they had a read depth higher than 0.7. Tandem and dispersed duplication sites were considered homozygous

if they had a relative read depth higher than 1.75, heterozygous if they had a relative read depth between 1.3 and 1.75, and non-variant if they had a read depth below 1.3. As we cannot determine the genotype of insertions based on read depth, insertions were assigned a genotype of unknown/variant (./1) by default. Genotypes of calls with a relative read depth higher than 4 or without any reads aligned in their 1000 bp flanking regions were considered to be unreliable and set to missing.

References

- Pedersen, B. S., & Quinlan, A. R. (2019). Duphold: Scalable, depth-based annotation and curation of high-confidence structural variant calls. *GigaScience*, 8, giz040.
- The 1001 Genomes Consortium. (2016). 1,135 genomes reveal the global pattern of polymorphism in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Cell*, 166(2), 481–491.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: **Differentially methylated CHG and CHH sites in plans of the fifth generation grown under different treatments.** (a) The number of differentially methylated CHG sites in individual plants of each treatment. (b) The number of differentially methylated CHH sites in individual plants of each treatment.

Figure S2: **Quality control of SNPs and small indels.** (a-d) Density plots of the variant annotations quality normalized by read depth (QD) (a), Fisher's exact test of strand bias (FS) (b), symmetric odds ratio test of strand bias (SOR) (c), and mapping quality (MQ) (d) of nuclear SNPs and small indels. Thresholds used to filter putative false positives are shown in red. Similar plots were used to filter mitochondrial and chloroplast variants.

Figure S3: **Mean SNP mutation rates at different thresholds for genotype quality (GQ) and the percentage of missing genotypes.** Although absolute rates change between different minimum GQ (a) and maximum allowed percentages of missing genotypes (b), relative differences between mutation rates are retained. Error bars depict standard errors of the mean. The same trends were seen when computing mutation rates of small insertions and deletions.